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A NOVEL METHODOLOGY TO QUANTIFY SHAPE COMPLEXITY OF COMPOSITE AEROSPACE PARTS

Mohammad T. Chowdhury¹, Thomas Turner²

¹Institute for Aerospace Technology, Innovation Park, Triumph Road, Nottingham NG7 2TU, United Kingdom. Email: mohammad.chowdhury@nottingham.ac.uk

²Department of Mechanical, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham NG7 2RD, United Kingdom. Email: thomas.turner@nottingham.ac.uk

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials are increasingly being used to produce aerospace parts due to their versatility when compared to metal counterparts. The design freedom afforded by composites and their manufacturing allow design engineers the possibility to create complex and integrated designs that save assembly weight and cost. This design activity takes place during early stages when there is a lack of information and hence it is easy to make miscalculated design modifications. This often leads to designs becoming overly complex and infeasible to manufacture; a consequence that will only be fully realised during the later stages. To quantify the complexity of designs, a metric called Shape Complexity SC has been developed. The SC data allows robust and informed decision making for factors such as whether part assemblies should be highly integrated (low part count) or more differentiated into more, but less complex, individual parts. In metals it is generally sufficient to quantify the geometric features and thus determine the SC value, however, composites additionally require the layup information to be quantified and current methods do not capture this. This developed SC metric addresses this by quantifying the layup information into Layup Complexity LC in addition to quantifying the geometric features into Geometric Complexity GC. This paper presents the novel methodology to quantify the shape complexity of composite aerospace parts that uses the limited amount of information of early design stages.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites materials are increasingly utilised in the aerospace industry to produce aircraft parts and the advantages of using composite materials over their metal counterparts are already well known [1]. Most Composite Manufacturing CM techniques follow Additive Manufacturing AM principles where composite materials are deposited in a layer by layer fashion to form a composite part. One of the benefits of this approach is that it allows the design of complex parts that are light-weight and require fewer assemblies. The potential weight and cost savings make composite materials and manufacturing an attractive option during design studies for aerospace.

The design activity of an aerospace part starts at the Conceptual Design Stage CDS where there is a large design space to work in and many different concepts are created. Critical decisions that direct the design and manufacturing of a part need to be taken at the CDS in order to proceed to the Preliminary Design Stage PDS and it is widely accepted that there is a lack of information at CDS [2, 3]. These decisions are critical because they will determine the path that a design will have to follow throughout the development process. Due to the obligation and lack of information, these critical decisions are often taken based on personal experience and historical data and this introduces biases into the design process. Biased decisions can direct the design programme towards an incorrect and misinformed course that can result in a suboptimal, unfeasible and overly complex design even in a concurrent engineering environment. Moreover, Design for Manufacturing and Assembly DfMA is not well established for composite materials and Design for Additive Manufacturing DfAM is still in its infancy in the same field [4-6]. So, there is a lack of established design guidelines which makes it challenging to keep track of design modifications and relationships between design and manufacturing parameters. These

relationships are essential to execute a data-driven method for part integration or differentiation during CDS rather than experience or FE based methods at later stages. Integration occurs when related subsections are joined together to form one integrated composite part whereas differentiation occurs when one discrete part is fragmented down into related subsections. Part integration saves on assembly costs and weight of the structure by reducing the need for fasteners and assembly processes but at the same time complicates the manufacturing process due to the integrated design. On the other hand, part differentiation simplifies and saves on manufacturing processes and costs by having an easier-to-build design but at the same time increases and complicates the assembly costs and processes because of the joining requirements. In addition to adding weight due to fasteners, differentiation also adds parasitic weight to the part due to strengthening requirements in regions where holes might be drilled. Several studies have indicated that design modifications are a significant barrier to design activities and major cost driver in manufacturing, so even small modifications to a design can have drastic effect on the manufacturing costs [7]. It is well-established that aircraft design activities account for almost 75-80% of design development costs. Studies have shown that reviewing any decisions taken during early CDS cost up to 13% more than reviewing any decisions taken during later stages and so there is great importance in getting decisions right at the first-time [8]. Generating new information by assessing the design and manufacturing parameters can aid in making informed decisions first time. Hence the authors propose the development of a new type of metric to evaluate designs called the Shape Complexity SC which can accommodate deposition processes and is adaptable to different types of composite manufacturing processes. The SC of a composite part is incomplete if the design features and the manufacturing processes are not considered together since both these factors are interconnected. Therefore, this paper seeks to demonstrate a novel methodology which considers both the design and manufacturing parameters to quantify the shape complexity of composite aerospace parts.

1.1 Definition of Shape Complexity for Composite Aerospace Parts

The definition for complexity is very broad and exists in many different science and engineering disciplines. SC in this paper refers to the difficulty associated with the production of the different design features present on a composite part and these features play a crucial role in forming the part by addition of composite materials. They also play an important role in defining the composite manufacturing processes that describe the geometry of the part. For metallic parts, these features are exclusively associated with the geometry, so it is sufficient to only consider the geometric information to determine the SC. However, due to the unique nature of composite parts being formed through the deposition of materials layer by layer or course by course, the layup information needs to be considered in addition to the geometric information to fully determine the SC.

The layup information consists of the important factors for the deposition process such as the level of curvature on the part, the number of full plies, the presence of ply patches and the material format/course type. These factors influence the difficulty associated with deposition process and they can be combined together to form the Layup Complexity LC. The geometric information consists of important factors that describe the geometry such as the size of the composite, presence of trimmed sections and drilled holes on the part. Similar to LC, these factors influence the magnitude of difficulty associated with processing the geometry of the composite part and can be combined to form the Geometric Complexity GC. The proposed SC of a composite aerospace part is a summation of both the LC and GC and the decomposition is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Decomposition of Shape Complexity

2 PREVIOUS WORK

Researchers have explored different ways to define the shape complexity of composite aerospace parts for different types of application. The ACCEM (Advanced Composite Cost Estimating Manual) was one of the earliest models to estimate the cost of various composite manufacturing activities. This empirical model emphasized 2 particular aspects of SC; however, this was insufficient as it only considered the bend profiles and fiber angles when determining the SC of a composite part [9]. Gutowski et al. authored a paper [10] where the authors developed a Complexity Factor CF. They theorized a hypothetical device that can measure and record the linear and angular deflection of fibers from a composite part to calculate CF. The obvious drawback is that this method requires an actual part to be physically available which would only be possible during the later manufacturing stages rather than early CDS. Moreover, the other factors that contribute towards the SC were not considered for the CF. Haffner proposed a detailed list of qualitative guidelines with respect to geometric complexity, size and production volume in his PhD thesis [11]. While textual descriptions are good at conveying qualitative information to describe the shape complexity of a part, they are not suitable for mathematical analysis because it is impractical to use qualitative texts for numerical operations. Also, the level of details can easily vary between different factors of the same design giving rise to resolution problems and inconsistency between them. Akermo et al. proposed another equation to calculate the shape complexity of a composite part which is the ratio of the projected area over the total surface area of the composite part [12]. This equation is simple and easy to use but it does not capture all of the factors required to completely define the SC such as the layup information. Other studies also follow a similar pattern of defining the complexity using different qualitative guidelines or pairwise comparison of certain factors. The key observation from these studies is that they do not follow any uniform methodology for the quantification process and are often highly specialized to very specific parts. This inconsistency between the methods give varying results for the same part when they are analyzed using the different methods. This creates a situation where personal biases take place because the method that will be chosen is going to be based on the user's preference and there is no knowledge to date of which one is the right one. Moreover, the specificity of the methods makes them inapplicable for a wide range of parts which is a major drawback since different aerospace parts are produced through different types of composite manufacturing techniques and none of the developed methods so far fits all. It is also important to note that the presence of detailed qualitative guidelines is evidence that current SC quantification methods are inadequate to fully describe a composite aerospace part. Finally, some of the methods require real physical parts and require very detailed manufacturing knowledge which design engineers at early CDS may not possess or be aware of, rendering these methods impractical during those stages.

2 DEVELOPMENT OF SHAPE COMPLEXITY

This proposed methodology uses basic manufacturing process flow, dimensions and layup information from the CAD model as the unbiased source of information during early stages. The SC is expressed in (1) where LC is the Layup Complexity, GC is the Geometric Complexity and T_T is the Total Time spent during the manufacturing of the composite part.

$$\text{Shape Complexity } SC = \frac{LC + GC}{T_T} \quad (1)$$

Each of the factors from Fig. 1 for LC and GC were first computed using a general form and then combined to form the LC and GC respectively. This generalised equation is expressed in (2);

$$C_x = T * A \quad (2)$$

Where C_x is the individual complexity metric for each of the factors, T is the time parameter and A is a design attribute for each of the respective factors. Any individual complexity metric can be only properly defined if both the design attributes and manufacturing processes are considered which is the case in (2). A is calculated using the information obtained from CAD model such as dimensions of the part, materials, part features and layup information. Similarly, T is calculated by constructing a manufacturing process flow for the part and estimating the time for each activity in the manufacturing process flow. The activities in the process flow depend on the design of the part so even slight differences in designs such as trimming using different types of cutting tools will eventually result in a

different process flow. Since different designs will have different activities, the estimated times will vary from one from process flow to another which allows for distinction between different manufacturing techniques or parameters. So, when one design is used to calculate the complexity metric for a factor produced using 2 different manufacturing techniques, T changes for each technique but A remains constant as the same design is being used. Similarly, when 2 different designs are used to calculate the complexity metric for a factor using the same manufacturing technique, A changes for each design but T remains constant. This particular formulation allows the complexity metrics to remain process independent and adaptable for new parts or processes.

2.1 Layup Complexity LC

The factors that affect the layup complexity are the number of full plies, occurrence of ply patches, material format/course type and presence of curvatures. Full ply number is the quantity of plies that are deposited and drawn-out till the EOP (edge of part). This includes any combination of material sizes as long as all of the deposited materials are at the same level and the total area for deposition is equal to the layup area of the part. Ply patches are pieces of plies whose total deposition area is smaller than the layup area of the part. Like full plies, ply patches can also be of different material sizes as long as they are deposited at the same level. Ply patches are typically used to aid the formation of certain part features like areas of high curvature or to save weight via reducing material usage by only reinforcing in high stress regions rather than the whole part. The course type is the format of material that is used for the deposition process such cut pieces of broad goods, slit tapes (widths less <300mm), discontinuous fibers etc. Each of the material format/course type have different deposition techniques and dimensions which will influence the deposition process of the part. Curvature is a part feature that is present on surfaces, corners and edges when a straight line or surface deviates at an angle. They are often challenging to produce, so even small curvatures can take a long time to form during the deposition process. Due to the unique nature of composite materials forming the part as material is being deposited, curvatures are formed during the deposition process rather than by post processing and ply patches are often used to gradually build the curvature rather than bending the part like in sheet metal forming. Combining all of these factors together form the LC shown in (3).

$$LC = \left\{ T_L \left(1 - \frac{A_p}{A_l} + \frac{l_{AB}}{C} \right) + nT_{L,1} \left(1 + \frac{A_p}{A_l} - \frac{W_c}{W_p} \right) - nT_{L,2} \left(\frac{l_{AB}}{C} \right) \right\} \quad (3)$$

Where T_L is the total time for layup, $T_{L,1}$ is the time for a single full layup, $T_{L,2}$ is the taken for flat layup, A_p is the area of the ply patch, A_l is the layup area, W_c is the width of the material, W_p is the longest width of the part, l_{AB} is the linear distance between the end points of an arc, n is the number of full layups and C is the arc length. It should also be noted that the orientation is not a factor for LC due to the fact that ply orientations are a structural requirement and the standard 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$, 90° ply orientations are always adhered to for most designs with no room for modifications.

2.2 Geometric Complexity GC

The factors that affect the geometric complexity are part characteristics such as the size of the composite part and part features such as presence of drilled holes and trimmed regions on the composite part. The size of a part defines its geometry and it is often biased in its measurement since it depends on the user's interpretation of what they think is a large sized part. In reality the size of a composite part is strongly co-related to its deposition technique because the size influences it. Certain processes which use automated deposition heads can easily accommodate large sized parts such as wing skins due to the bigger machines and tools. At the same time, wing skins are very difficult to produce using manual methods because of their larger dimensions. Presence of drilled holes also define the geometry and the geometric information of the part is incomplete if drilled holes are not considered. Even though holes are subjected to standards which are generally not considered during the early CDS, they are strongly related to the level of part integration or differentiation. Finally, trimmed regions are also used to describe the geometry and is a geometric feature. Trimmed regions are areas where additional material is cut and discarded from a near net shaped part. The analogy for including holes and trimmed sections

can be described such that a hollow composite tube will only be described as a composite barrel, however when holes are drilled in for spars and the windows and door sections are cut off then it can be described as a fuselage. Combining all of these factors form the GC shown in (4).

$$GC = \left\{ T_G \left(\frac{PA_p}{SA_t} \right) + T_{G,1} \left(\frac{V_r}{V_p} \right) + T_{G,2} \left(\frac{l_c}{p} \right) \right\} \quad (4)$$

Where T_G is the total time for machining, $T_{G,1}$ is the total time for drilling operation, $T_{G,2}$ is the total time for trimming operation, PA_p is the projected area of the part, SA_t is the surface area of the tool, V_r is the volume of material removed, V_p is the part volume, l_c is the total length of the cut and p is the perimeter of the part.

3 CASE STUDY

The following case study highlights the importance of quantifying the shape complexity of a composite part. This case study is conducted using the designs of 2 similar composite wing spars; wing spar 1 and wing spar 2 as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Design of composite wing spars 1 and 2

Both the wing spars have a length of 400mm, outer depth of 40mm and inner width of 70mm. Wing spar 1 has 8 drilled holes of 10mm in diameter and spar 2 has 16 drilled holes of 5mm in diameter. Additionally, spar 1 is produced with fiber tows of width 6.35mm deposited using an automated deposition head and has ply patches. Spar 2 is produced with prepreg tapes of 101.6mm deposited using hand layup and has larger ply patches when compared to wing spar 1.

During early CDS, the comparative study between these two designs is very complicated because there are 4 different parameters which are different between them; the manufacturing method, the size of ply patches, the course type and a feature (drilled holes). Some of these parameters have a magnitude such as diameter of the drilled holes and size of ply patches while the parameters do not have any magnitude associated with them such as manufacturing method and course type. The information presented here are not of the same format and this poses a challenge for comparative study.

To overcome this, both these designs could be either compared qualitatively using textual descriptions which means converting the numbers into text or conducting a pairwise scoring using methods such as Analytical Hierarchical Process which involves assigning numbers to descriptions. On one hand, converting numbers into textual information make them impractical for numerical operations and on the other hand, converting textual information into numbers through pairwise scoring distort the uniqueness between the different parameters. In both cases, these methods are prone to high levels of personal bias. Qualitative texts and pairwise scoring are dependent on the user's understanding of composites and their personal interpretation of the design which can vary for each individual.

In order to prevent this dilemma, shape complexity can be used as a means to quantitatively compare two designs. Using the information extracted from the CAD models of each design, the LC, GC and resultant SC of wing spars 1 and 2 is calculated and shown in Table 1. A process flow for each wing spar was constructed to estimate the time for each activity in the flow. Spar 1 have tool preparation, machine preparation, deposition, consolidation, drilling and trimming for its respective process flow.

Spar 2 have tool preparation, material preparation, deposition, consolidation, drilling and trimming for its respective process flow. The summation of the time of all the activities for each flow is the total time for manufacturing T_T .

Wing spar 1				Wing spar 2			
Layup		Geometry		Layup		Geometry	
n	10	l_c (m)	2.60×10^{-1}	n	10	l_c (m)	2.60×10^{-1}
C (m)	7.85×10^{-3}	p (m)	1.06	C (m)	1.10×10^{-2}	p (m)	1.06
l_{AB} (m)	7.07×10^{-3}	PA_p (m ²)	3.60×10^{-2}	l_{AB} (m)	9.90×10^{-3}	PA_p (m ²)	3.60×10^{-2}
W_c (m)	6.35×10^{-3}	SA_t (m ²)	2.50×10^{-1}	W_c (m)	1.02×10^{-1}	SA_t (m ²)	2.50×10^{-1}
W_p (m)	4.00×10^{-1}	V_p (m ³)	5.91×10^{-4}	W_p (m)	4.00×10^{-1}	V_p (m ³)	5.90×10^{-4}
A_p (m ²)	5.25×10^{-3}	V_r (m ³)	1.26×10^{-5}	A_p (m ²)	8.00×10^{-3}	V_r (m ³)	6.28×10^{-6}
A_l (m ²)	6.80×10^{-2}	T_G (s)	730s	A_l (m ²)	6.80×10^{-2}	T_G (s)	840s
T_L (s)	900s	$T_{G,1}$ (s)	310s	T_L (s)	2500s	$T_{G,1}$ (s)	480s
$T_{L,1}$ (s)	60s	$T_{G,2}$ (s)	240s	$T_{L,1}$ (s)	240s	$T_{G,2}$ (s)	240s
$T_{L,2}$ (s)	58s			$T_{L,2}$ (s)	150s		
LC	1752.02s	GC	170.60s	LC	5171.20s	GC	184.94s
SC	1.18			SC	1.60		

Table 1: LC, GC and SC values for wing spars 1 and 2

The results from the table approximately show that wing spar 1 has a LC of 1752s, a GC of 171s and a resultant SC of 1.18. Wing spar 2 approximately has a LC of 5171s, a GC of 185s and a resultant SC of 1.60 which makes wing spar 2 more complex than wing spar 1.

4 DISCUSSION

The LC increased by 195.16% by changing the manufacturing method and material course format from automated fiber deposition to manual prepreg deposition and increasing the size of the ply patches for wing spar 2. The GC increased by 8.41% by doubling the number of holes from 8 to 16 for wing spar 2. These complexities when combined together show that wing spar 2 increased its shape complexity by 35.60% when compared to wing spar 1 due to change in 4 parameters. The results are illustrated in Figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3: Comparison of LC and GC between wing spar 1 and 2

Figure 4: Comparison of SC for Wing spar 1 and 2

Without this shape complexity metric, the change in manufacturing method and course type can only be described through descriptive texts and the size of ply patches and number of holes can only be described through their magnitudes. This does not help with analysis because these textual descriptions do not signify the transformation that occurs on the design as a result of the modification. Moreover, there is an inconsistency in the format between the factors and this makes it difficult to conduct any form of useful analysis mainly because it is easier to make decisions using results that are derived from numerical analysis rather than textual descriptions. The LC, GC and resulting SC metrics are particularly useful information to have during early CDS as they inform the user about the design transformation that occurs due to the modifications made. A positive percentage will show that the modifications increased the shape complexity of the newer design whereas a negative percentage will show that the modifications decreased the shape complexity of the newer design. In addition to understanding the transformation of the design modification, a user can also use the SC metrics to compare between different competing designs to choose the best option. As mentioned above, this traditionally would have been conducted using pairwise scoring methods which are subjected to biases and inconsistent scoring. The SC metrics are derived using data retrieved from CAD model which remains as the only unbiased and consistent source of information during early CDS. Users are also able to discover the level of influence between different parameters in a design by using the SC metric. This can be done by changing one parameter and keeping the others constant to calculate its influence on the LC, GC and SC of the part. By this method previously unknown relationships can be produced between different parameters during early CDS which will be useful for design studies. It will help realize the factors that can affect the layout or machining operation of a part during the manufacturing stages. Furthermore, the shape complexity metrics can be used a tool for part integration or differentiation for composite aerospace parts. A 3-axis graph of shape complexity vs number of related subsections vs total time for manufacture and assembly can be constructed. Based on the graph, the most ideal number of related subsections can be chosen which has the most ideal shape complexity and the most acceptable total time for manufacturing and assembly.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper proposes a new methodology to quantify the shape complexity of composite aerospace parts. The procedure begins by dividing the shape complexity into the layout complexity which contain information regarding the layout of the part and the geometric complexity which contain information regarding the geometry of the part. Equations were developed to quantify this information and calculate the LC and GC. The resultant SC is a combination of both the LC and GC and this is demonstrated using two composite wing spars. The methodology separates the design activity from the manufacturing activity by quantifying the design attributes and manufacturing parameters separately. The case study shows the significance of the developing a shape complexity and how it can be used for comparison and trade-offs during design studies at early CDS. CAD softwares are getting embedded with more complex features at the moment, so the developers can develop non-trivial tools for automated process flow generation while the model is being designed on CAD. This will give engineers an early visual representation of the path which a design will take throughout its development cycle and further facilitate shape complexity calculations.

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